

The Role and Operation of BIOS in x86 IA-16 and IA-32 Architectures During System Initialization

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Abstract

The x86 IA-32 architecture, based on the IA-16 architecture, has remained one of the most widely used computing platforms for decades, thanks to its backward compatibility and standardized system boot mechanisms. Within this architecture, the Basic Input/Output System (BIOS) is a fundamental firmware component responsible for initializing the hardware and executing the early stages of the boot process before the operating system takes control. This study systematically examines the historical development, core functions, and interaction with hardware during the boot process of the BIOS in x86-based systems. In particular, the BIOS interrupt mechanism, which provides low-level hardware access in real mode, is discussed. Additionally, IBM BIOS interrupt tables are provided as supplementary material for technical reference. This study systematically addresses the role and operation of the BIOS in x86 platforms within a technical framework.

Keywords: BIOS, firmware, x86 architecture, real mode, POST, bootloading

1. Introduction

In computer systems, starting from the moment power is supplied, the initialization of hardware and the loading of the operating system require a specific boot mechanism. This mechanism is executed by the firmware layer, which acts as a bridge between the hardware and the operating system. For many years, this task was undertaken by the BIOS [1].

The x86 architecture has maintained its widespread use for many years due to its backward compatibility approach. The Intel 80386 (Intel 386), the first 32-bit processor of the IA-32 architecture family, sustained this compatibility approach by preserving the real mode execution environment that first emerged with the Intel 8086 and 8088 processors [2]. This

approach was further reinforced by the virtual 8086 mode, which enables software developed for real mode to run on more advanced processor environments [2, 3]. In line with these architectural features, BIOS persisted as the primary platform firmware solution on legacy x86 platforms for an extended period. However, due to BIOS's operation model specific to older platforms, Intel has announced that legacy BIOS boot support will be removed from modern platforms [4].

In addition, Intel developed the Extensible Firmware Interface (EFI), which aimed to address the restrictive issues of BIOS and is used in more modern systems. This structure was later developed by the UEFI Forum and transformed into the Unified Extensible Firmware Interface (UEFI) standard [5, 6, 7].

Although UEFI specifications define firmware standards in modern computing platforms, the architectural foundation of backward compatibility, which is a characteristic feature of the x86 architecture, and the bootstrapping processes are based on the x86 reset and initialization model [8]. Examining the processes from the processor executing its first instruction via the reset vector to the system's transition to protected mode reveals the layered structure of hardware–firmware–software interaction [8].

When existing academic studies are examined, it is observed that research in the firmware domain largely focuses on security vulnerabilities, malicious firmware analysis, forensic data acquisition methods, and UEFI exploitation techniques. However, comprehensive studies that systematically address BIOS's memory mapping design decisions within a historical and architectural context are limited. Fundamental design choices, such as the 1 megabyte (MB) memory limit of BIOS, the positioning of the reset vector, and the placement of the Interrupt Vector Table (IVT), have mostly been explained at

the level of technical documentation; however, the underlying reasons for these decisions and their lasting impacts on modern firmware models have not been evaluated within a holistic analytical framework. To the best of our knowledge, there is no comprehensive review study that systematically examines the historical development of the legacy BIOS architecture, its memory mapping strategies, and the repercussions of these design choices on UEFI-based modern platforms.

In this direction, this study conducted a structured literature review on vendor technical documents, processor architecture manuals, firmware specifications, and relevant academic publications published between 1979 and 2025. The findings obtained reveal the historical origins of the BIOS memory model and evaluate the operation of this architectural legacy on x86 IA-16 and IA-32 platforms within an analytical framework.

2. Architectural Structure of BIOS and Its Fundamental Components

This section provides information on the definition of BIOS, its location within computer memory and on the motherboard, as well as the hardware components that assist in its operation. Additionally, the history of BIOS is discussed, and the emergence of certain architectural limitations is addressed. Thus, the subsequent sections will better elucidate how BIOS operates.

2.1 History of BIOS

The term BIOS was first used in the literature by Dr. Gary Kildall in the context of the CP/M (Control Program for Microcomputers) operating system. Developed in 1974, CP/M defined a separate layer called BIOS by separating the hardware-dependent code sections from the main operating system kernel. This structure enabled hardware-specific routines to be collected in a separate module and allowed the operating system to operate relatively independently of the hardware. Thus, the same CP/M kernel could be executed on different microcomputer platforms by adapting only the BIOS layer [9]. CP/M consists of a Console Command Processor (CCP), a Basic Disk Operating System (BDOS), and BIOS [10]. Figure-1 provides the memory addresses where the CCP, BDOS, and BIOS are located within CP/M.

Figure-1: CP/M memory layout [10]

2.1.1 CP/M and CCP

In the CP/M architecture, the CCP is the command interpreter layer that provides user interaction. While the system is idle, it is the CCP's task to receive and interpret commands. When a program is executed, the memory occupied by the CCP becomes available for use by the program, and the CCP is temporarily disabled. Upon program completion, the CCP is reloaded; this process is referred to as a warm boot, which affects only the CCP and does not touch the BDOS and BIOS layers. The program signals to CP/M that it has finished by jumping to address 0000H, and the BIOS warm start routine is activated. Thus, the CCP is reloaded from disk and control is transferred back to the CCP [10].

2.1.2 CP/M and BDOS

The CCP and all programs running under CP/M communicate with the BDOS for external connections. While the BDOS performs logical tasks such as console input/output, printer output, and file management, low-level hardware operations are executed together with the BIOS. When a program wants to call the BDOS, it uses a specific jump instruction placed in memory. During a cold boot, the BIOS places the instruction that jumps to the warm boot routine at address 0000H, and adds a jump instruction at address 0005H that transfers control to the first instruction of the BDOS. In this way, programs send a CALL instruction to 0005H, enabling the BDOS to complete the relevant task, and upon completion, control returns to the calling program. Specific values placed in the CPU registers before the BDOS call determine which operation will be performed and the necessary parameters [10].

2.1.3 CP/M and BIOS

In the CP/M architecture, while the BDOS performs logical input/output tasks independently of the physical details of the computer hardware, direct communication with the hardware and peripheral devices is provided by the BIOS. This distinction between the BDOS and the BIOS is one of the fundamental reasons why CP/M could operate compatibly on different hardware platforms. The same CP/M version, while keeping identical copies of the CCP and BDOS, could run smoothly on nearly 200,000 computers by only making the BIOS layer hardware-specific. The BDOS directs the appropriate BIOS entry point to perform the required operation; each entry point is configured as an independent instruction of three bytes in length, and all of these instructions constitute the BIOS jump table. If programmers access the BIOS directly instead of the BDOS, portability is compromised; therefore, CP/M applications should be designed to communicate only with the BDOS. Thus, the functional separation between the CCP, BDOS, and BIOS layers ensures both system flexibility and the ability of programs to run on different CP/M versions without requiring modifications [10]. All of these layers and the boot process are managed by the CP/M Bootstrap Loader, which is loaded into memory via PROM (programmable read-only memory)-based firmware on the computer [10].

2.2 Definition of Firmware and Its Use in Computers

Firmware is a term initially used to refer to the BIOS code stored in ROM on the motherboard, which enabled hardware initialization in personal computers. Over time, the concept expanded to encompass software stored in persistent memory on microcontrollers and embedded systems that provides direct hardware control. Although the boundary between firmware and traditional software has become somewhat blurred today, firmware is fundamentally defined as low-level control software that operates in close interaction with hardware and is typically located in non-volatile memory [11].

2.3 Role of BIOS and Its Location as Firmware

BIOS is the first platform firmware layer executed after the processor reset in x86-based systems. The processor begins execution from the starting address defined in the reset vector [8]. The primary function of BIOS is to perform the initial configuration of system memory, the chipset, interrupt controllers, and basic input/output devices, and then prepare a bootable environment. Throughout this process, BIOS runs the processor in real mode and provides low-level service routines that enable direct hardware access [11, 13]. Architecturally, BIOS functions as a temporary abstraction

layer between the hardware and the operating system. It provides fundamental hardware services before the operating system is loaded, but once control is taken over by the boot loader, the role of BIOS is largely completed. Therefore, although BIOS is system software, its execution time is limited to the system startup phase. On legacy x86 platforms, BIOS is typically stored in non-volatile memory on the motherboard and is executed by being mapped into the address space during system boot [11]. On modern platforms, this structure has been replaced by UEFI-based firmware architecture [6].

2.4 Memory Layout of BIOS

In the x86 architecture, the first 1 MB of memory address space has historically been divided into specific functional regions. The range from 0 to 640 KB (0x00000 – 0xA0000) is traditionally referred to as conventional memory or the DOS area, and denotes the standard DRAM (Dynamic Random Access Memory) region used by legacy operating systems or boot loader code. The range from 640 to 768 KB (0xA0000 – 0xC0000) is historically reserved for the video buffer, and depending on the system configuration, it may also be used as SMRAM (System Management RAM) or mapped as a memory-mapped I/O area. The region from 768 to 896 KB (0xC0000 – 0xE0000) is reserved for legacy expansion (option) ROMs; this area is typically DRAM and can be locked by the system to be read-only. Finally, the range from 896 KB to 1 MB (0xE0000 – 0x100000) represents the system BIOS area; this region may be either directly DRAM or configured as a memory-mapped I/O area mapped to flash memory [14, 15, 16]. Figure-2 visualizes these memory addresses.

Figure-2: Computer memory address map [16]

2.5 Hardware Components of BIOS

Every computer has a motherboard that stores the BIOS in ROM or flash memory. ROM is permanent, while flash memory is non-volatile and can be updated by the operating system when errors are found in the BIOS [17]. Figure-3 shows an example of a BIOS ROM.

Figure-3: Example BIOS ROM

When the computer is turned on, the BIOS is initialized, and the BIOS then determines the boot device by trying the list of devices stored in Complementary Metal-Oxide-Semiconductor (CMOS) memory. The CMOS contains date and time information, hardware settings, and boot configuration. Since CMOS is volatile, it is powered by the CMOS battery, thus preserving the data within it even when the computer is unplugged [17]. Figure-4 shows an example of a CMOS battery.

Figure-4: Example of a CMOS CR2032 Battery

3. x86 Reset Architecture and System Startup Process

In an x86-based system, the startup process is not merely about loading the operating system, but refers to a layered architectural chain that begins with the processor being placed into a reset state following the application of power. After the power supply ensures voltage stabilization, the processor is forced into a defined initial state via the RESET#

signal and begins executing its first instruction from the architecturally determined reset vector [8, 18]. This point is the critical threshold at which hardware control is transferred to the platform firmware residing in non-volatile memory. This mechanism involves interrelated stages such as the initial configuration of the processor micro-architecture, memory address mapping, and the establishment of the firmware execution environment. In this section, the architectural fundamentals of the x86 reset model are examined, and the process occurring from power application to the execution of BIOS is systematically addressed.

3.1 Power Stabilization and RESET# Mechanism

When power is applied to an x86-based system, the processor does not start operating directly. The computer's Power Supply Unit (PSU) generates the Power Good (PWR_OK) signal, which indicates that the output voltage has reached a stable level [19]. When this signal is brought to a high level, the system power supply, through the converter, has stored sufficient energy to guarantee uninterrupted power operation for the minimum hold-up time according to the power supply specifications [20]. After power-on or when the RESET# pin is activated, each processor on the system bus performs a hardware initialization (or hardware reset) [8].

3.2 Post-Reset Micro-Architectural State of the Processor

An x86 IA-32 architecture processor provides 16 basic processor registers for use in general system and application programming [3]. In addition to these processor registers, there are also control registers named CR0, CR2, CR3, and CR4 [21]. These control registers contain various flags and data fields for controlling system-level operations. Other flags in these registers are used to indicate support for specific processor capabilities within the operating system or execution unit [8]. When the processor performs a hardware reset, the CR0 register state is set to 60000010H, thus placing the processor into real mode without paging [21]. Table-1 provides the reset values of some registers within an IA-32 architecture processor.

Table-1: Reset Values of 32-bit Registers [8]

Register Name	Value After Reset
EFLAGS	0000002H
EIP	0000FFF0H
CR0	60000010H
CS	Selector = F000H Base = FFFF0000H Limit = FFFFH AR = Present, R/W, Accessed
	Selector = 0000H

SS, DS, ES, FS, GS	Base = 00000000H Limit = FFFFH AR = Present, R/W, Accessed
EDX	000n06xxH
EAX	0
EBX, ECX, ESI, EDI, EBP, ESP	00000000H

3.2.1 Real Mode

Real mode implements the programming environment of the Intel 8086 processor, along with extensions (such as transitioning to protected or system management modes). The processor is placed into real mode after power-on or a reset operation [8]. In this mode, instructions and the operands used for instructions are 16-bit in length. Additionally, real mode does not include a security mechanism to prevent the execution of malicious programs. Furthermore, in a processor with real mode active, the memory space can directly access a maximum of 1 MB area [22]. This area represents the addresses between 0x00000 and 0xFFFFF.

3.2.2 Segmentation

Due to the active real mode, certain methods are used to access addresses within the 1 MB memory space. One of these methods is segmentation. The physical address is calculated using segmentation as shown with Formula 1. The sum of the segment (S) multiplied by 16 and the offset (O) gives the physical address (PA) value [23].

$$PA = (S \times 16) + O \quad (1)$$

In computers, the segment:offset notation is used for writing segmentation. For example, the expression 12F3:4B27 corresponds to the physical address 0x17A57. Thus, within real mode, physical addresses can be written using this mechanism [23].

3.2.3 A20 Line

As explained in Section 3.2.2, addressing in real mode is based on a 20-bit physical address generation mechanism using the segment:offset pair. This structure limits the memory area that the processor can directly address to 1 MB. However, when this limit is exceeded, the address wrap-around problem occurs. For example, when 0x1 is added to the physical address 0xFFFFF, although the expected result is 0x100000, due to the limitation of the 20-bit address bus, the address wraps around to 0x00000 [23, 24].

The Intel 8086 processor has a total of 20 address lines, only A0–A19, which makes this wrapping behavior a hardware necessity. With the Intel 80286 processor, the address bus was expanded to provide a total of 24-bit physical addressing

support, namely A0–A23. Thus, access to a theoretical physical memory space of 16 MB (2^{24} bytes) became possible. However, due to the backward compatibility requirement of the 80286, the 1 MB address wrap-around behavior of the 8086 needed to be preserved. For this purpose, the A20 line was made controllable and could be disabled when necessary to emulate the 20-bit addressing behavior. When the A20 line is disabled, addressing exhibits wrap-around behavior at the 1 MB boundary, whereas when it is enabled, access to physical addresses above 1 MB is possible [23, 24].

3.3 Transferring Control to Firmware via the Reset Vector

As long as the RESET signal is active on the processor, the processor does not execute any instructions, and no activity occurs on the data bus [25]. After the processor reset line is deactivated, the processor begins fetching instructions. The location from which these instructions begin to be fetched is known as the reset vector. The reset vector may contain instructions or a pointer to the actual initial instruction sequence in flash memory. The location of the vector is architecture-specific and is generally at a fixed position depending on the processor [26]. This location is 0xFFFFF0 on 16-bit processors, while on 32-bit processors it is the address 0xFFFFFFFFF0 [8, 27, 28].

In the 80386 architecture, the execution address after reset is defined as 0xFFFFFFFFF0. This address is not the result of real mode segment:offset calculation. In the 'reset' state, the processor forces the upper 12 bits of the addresses generated for the code segment to '1', directing execution to the uppermost part of the address space. This enables the firmware code to be placed in the upper region of the memory map. The first instruction is expected to be a far jump; after this jump is executed, the upper bits of the addresses generated for the code segment are cleared, and execution returns to the normal real mode addressing model [29]. On 32-bit x86 processors, the reset vector is physically at address 0xFFFFFFFFF0 because during reset, the processor loads the CS register with F000h, the EIP register with 0000FFF0h, and the CS base with FFFF0000h. This execution address is calculated as the sum of CS base and EIP ($0xFFFF0000 + 0xFFF0 = 0xFFFFFFFFF0$) [30]. Since only 16 bytes remain at the top of memory, this area must contain a far jump to the rest of the initialization code. Because there is no software stack or cache yet, this code is always written in assembly language. RAM is not yet available at this stage [26].

3.3.1 Early Initialization and Memory Configuration

In the early stages of system startup, since DRAM has not yet been configured, the processor initially operates without a

software stack. To overcome this limitation, modern processors allow the cache to be temporarily used as RAM (Cache-as-RAM – CAR) [26]. However, because main memory is not available, eviction of cache lines can lead to critical issues; therefore, some processors use modes such as No-Eviction Mode (NEM) to prevent cache lines from being evicted [31]. DRAM initialization varies depending on the technology and platform used; on Intel systems, this process is typically carried out through the Memory Reference Code (MRC) [26]. In the absence of MRC, the initialization sequences defined by JEDEC are followed, and memory timings, bank structures, capacity, and layout parameters are configured in a chipset-specific manner [26]. On removable memory modules, configuration information is read via SPD EEPROM and determined through SMBus; on soldered (memory-down) designs, the configuration may be fixed [26].

3.3.2 Operations After Memory Initialization

After the memory controller is initialized, memory testing and integrity verification operations are performed. On current platforms, these tests are mostly executed within the scope of the MRC; however, depending on design requirements, additional verifications may be applied [26]. A balance must be established between test coverage and system boot time; fast startup is particularly prioritized in embedded and mobile systems [26]. On systems with Error-Correcting Code (ECC) support, due to this mechanism used to ensure data integrity, inconsistencies may occur between memory content and ECC bits after power-on; therefore, a write operation to memory is applied to synchronize ECC bits, and depending on security requirements, memory content may be zeroed [26]. Depending on the restart type, these operations may not always be repeated; in warm restart scenarios, memory context may be preserved, or the early initialization process may be re-executed due to configuration changes [26].

3.3.3 Shadow Memory

ROMs are used by components that require their own instructions to function properly. Examples of such components include a graphics card or a cache disk controller. An alternative method is to load the instructions from the disk each time they are needed. ROMs are 8-bit devices, which means that 1 byte can be accessed at a time. With access times of approximately 150–400 ns for these ROMs, RAM, which is 32-bit memory, can provide access with a duration of 60–80 ns and, additionally, can access 4 bytes of data [32, 33]. These timings may vary from device to device.

Since attempting to read code from ROM is slower compared to reading from RAM, if the system supports it, the ROM content is copied to RAM, and this process is called 'shadowing memory' [26, 33]. The system BIOS is located in

the 64 KB address area between F0000h and FFFFFh on ISA systems (and in the 128 KB area between E0000h and FFFFFh on EISA systems) [33]. Thus, the BIOS content is executed more quickly.

3.4 Power-On Self Test (POST) Routine

When the computer is turned on, a far jump is executed from the reset vector, and the BIOS routine is initiated. This routine is called POST, and its primary function is to initialize hardware components and perform system tests. During POST, fundamental hardware such as the processor, memory, interrupt controller, and DMA controller are tested. Additionally, the video card and other expansion cards are also initialized at this stage. In the event of an error, POST generates a display message or a warning signal through the speaker [34].

When POST tests are successfully completed, ROM extensions are searched for. These extensions aim to extend or modify the existing BIOS routines and are typically used for EGA/VGA cards or hard disk controllers. BIOS scans for ROM extensions within specific memory ranges and loads their initialization routines.

After the initialization of ROM extensions, the boot process linked to BIOS is activated. Through Interrupt 19H (bootstrap loader), the system attempts to load the operating system from a predetermined disk location. If the disk is not found or system files are missing, other drives are tried; if no suitable disk is found, older systems revert to ROM BASIC, while modern systems prompt the user to insert a disk [34]. Following successful POST and ROM extension scanning, the computer becomes ready to load the operating system.

3.4.1 APM and BIOS

Advanced Power Management (APM) consists of one or more software layers that support power management in computers with power-manageable hardware, and provides a hardware-independent software interface between the hardware-specific power management software and the operating system power management policy driver. It works together with the BIOS. The APM BIOS is the software interface between the motherboard and power-managed devices and components. The APM BIOS performs power management in the background based on device activity. The APM BIOS is provided by the OEM (Original Equipment Manufacturer) and is specific to the hardware platform. An APM system has five general system power states. These are Full On, APM Enabled, APM Standby, APM Suspend, and Off. The primary difference between the states is the latency required for the system to return to the operational state. Power consumption and performance are highest in the Full

On state and decrease with each state. APM states are defined in general terms and allow implementation variations [35]. In modern systems, this process is handled not by APM but by the Advanced Configuration and Power Interface (ACPI) [18].

3.5 Transferring Control to the Bootloader and the Role of BIOS

For a computer to start operating (for example, when powered on or restarted), an initial program to execute is required [36]. The first program used for this purpose is called the bootstrap loader, and it is typically stored in the firmware located in non-volatile memory on the system motherboard. When the system is started, this small program is executed and performs the initialization of fundamental hardware components. It then loads and executes a more comprehensive boot program located at a specific position on a secondary storage device. This process creates the initial environment necessary for transferring the operating system from the storage device to memory and bringing the system into an operational state [36].

After the startup operations performed by the firmware are completed, control is transferred to the bootloader. At this stage, the bootloader continues to prepare the necessary execution environment for loading the operating system. Operations such as arranging the CPU state, preparing memory usage, and providing basic device access are carried out at this stage. Thus, the bootloader acts as a bridge between the firmware and the operating system, enabling the system to be fully started [37].

Initially, the BIOS loads the boot file from the secondary storage device to main memory at address 0x7C00 and executes the boot process [38]. On Windows platforms, this boot file is called the Master Boot Record (MBR). For booting to occur, the firmware instructs the system to read the bootloader code within the MBR, and the MBR, in addition to containing the boot code, includes a table listing the partitions on the disk drive and a flag indicating which partition the system will boot from. After the system determines the boot partition, it reads the first sector/page from this partition (referred to as the boot sector), which then directs it to the kernel. Subsequently, it continues with the rest of the boot process, which involves loading various subsystems and system services [36]. Figure-5 visualizes this process.

Figure-5: Boot from a Storage Device in Windows [36]

3.5.1 Master Boot Record Structure

The MBR is located in the first sector (0x00) of the hard drive. It contains the most essential terms for initializing the device and loading the operating system into memory. It is a disk data structure created after the disk is partitioned. Disk partitioning means the logical distribution of the hard drive into multiple storage units, allowing different file systems to be used on each partition. The MBR is found only on partitioned storage devices and cannot be found on unpartitioned disks such as floppy disks. The MBR consists of the disk's partition table and locates the bootable disk, which are referred to as active partitions. It also contains information about the type and size of the partitions and the file systems used on each logical partition. Within the MBR, the boot code section is 446 bytes, the partition table is 64 bytes, and the last two bytes of this 512-byte record consist of the Boot Record Signature, known as the 'magic number,' with a value of 0xAA55 [39]. Figure-6 visualizes this structure.

Figure-6: MBR Structure

When the MBR is loaded, the BIOS checks the last two bytes of the sector. The last two bytes must contain the HEX values 55AA. If this boot record signature is not present, error messages such as "insert boot disk" or "non-system boot" will appear [40]. On Little-Endian systems, the value 0xAA55 is found in memory as '55 AA' [41].

4. BIOS Interrupt Mechanism

During the boot phase, the BIOS provides many fundamental services for controlling the hardware. A service is a set of routines that controls a specific hardware device or returns information about the current system [42]. Each service is assigned an interrupt number [42]. The BIOS is accessed

through software interrupts, and each BIOS entry point can be accessed via its own interrupt [13]. An interrupt is a signal from a peripheral device or a program's request to perform a specific service (Interrupt Request - IRQ). When an interrupt is triggered, the processor is alerted to suspend the currently running process and jump to the Interrupt Service Routine (ISR), i.e., the interrupt handler. When a program is suspended, the processor saves the contents of the CS and IP registers onto the stack and initiates the interrupt routine. After the interrupt routine completes its task, it issues the IRET (Interrupt Return) instruction, which restores the contents of the CS and IP registers from the stack, thereby resuming the program. The interrupt routine saves and restores the contents of other registers before returning to the interrupted program [43, 44]. Figure-7 visualizes this operation.

Figure-7: Interrupt Routine Operation [43]

4.1 Interrupt Vector Table Structure

The 8088 processor can potentially have 256 interrupts (0-255). Each interrupt has an associated interrupt routine to handle the specific condition. To organize the 256 interrupts, the starting addresses of the relevant interrupt routines are arranged in the Interrupt Vector Table. When an interrupt occurs, the processor automatically retrieves the starting address of the interrupt routine from the interrupt vector table. The starting address of each interrupt routine is specified in the table in terms of the offset address and the segment address. Both addresses are 16 bits (2 bytes) wide. Therefore, each table entry occupies 4 bytes. The total length of the table is 1 KB [43]. Figure-8 visualizes this structure.

Figure-8: Interrupt Vector Table Structure [43]

The Interrupt Vector Table is located in memory between addresses 0x0 and 0x3FF. To calculate the starting address (SA) of an interrupt, it is sufficient to multiply the interrupt number (IN) by four [43]. Formula 2 can be used for the calculation.

$$SA = IN \times 4 \quad (2)$$

4.2 BIOS Service Interrupt Routines

Interrupts are divided into two main types: hardware and software. Figure-9 visualizes these interrupt types.

Figure-9: Interrupt Types [43]

Software interrupts are mechanisms triggered via the INT instruction used in machine language programs, notifying the processor that a specific interrupt is being called through the interrupt number specified within the instruction. Through this structure, programs can directly call the fundamental services provided by the operating system; these services can be used both at the assembler level and from high-level programming languages that support interrupt handling. Hardware interrupts, on the other hand, are triggered by

external hardware components such as the keyboard or disk drive, and enable efficient processing of events occurring in the system. These interrupts are divided into two types: maskable and non-maskable. While maskable interrupts can be temporarily disabled by the processor, non-maskable interrupts are designed to always be processed, intended for reporting critical conditions such as system errors. Additionally, there are internal hardware interrupts generated by the processor itself. For example, timer interrupts generated at regular intervals by the timer are used for system timing and controlling certain hardware functions [43].

Interrupts can be used with the INT instruction and the interrupt number. The AH register indicates which specific routine within the general interrupt function is executed [13]. Table-2 provides the numbers and functions of some interrupts found in the IBM PS/2 in tabular form.

Table-2: Types and Functions of Some Interrupts Found in the IBM PS/2 [13, 43]

Interrupt Number	Type	Function
00H	Software	Division by Zero
02H	Software	Non-Maskable Interrupt
05H	Software	Printing to Screen
08H	Hardware (IRQ0)	System Timer
09H	Hardware (IRQ1)	Keyboard Operations
10H	Hardware (IRQ2)	Video Operations
11H	Hardware (IRQ3)	Equipment Determination Operations
12H	Hardware (IRQ4)	Memory Size Determination Operations
13H	Hardware (IRQ5)	Floppy Disk and Hard Disk Operations
14H	Hardware (IRQ6)	Asynchronous Communication Operations
15H	Hardware (IRQ7)	System Services
16H	Hardware (IRQ8)	Keyboard Operations
17H	Hardware (IRQ9)	Printer Operations
19H	Software	Bootstrap Loader Operations
1AH	Software	System Timer and Real-Time Clock

		Services Operations
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Thus, through interrupts, communication with computer hardware can be established using the BIOS.

4.3 Hardware Access in Real Mode

The interrupt services provided by the BIOS enable fundamental hardware operations to be performed during the boot process. In particular, disk access operations are executed using interrupt calls performed through BIOS disk services. Interrupt 13H is concerned with disk access and can read a disk sector specified by the code during computer boot. Figure-10 provides an example of Assembly code using interrupt 13H.

```

org 0x7c00

bits 16

start: jmp boot

boot:
cli
cld

mov ax, 0x50
mov es, ax
xor bx, bx

mov al, 2
mov ch, 0
mov cl, 2
mov dh, 0
mov dl, 0

mov ah, 0x02
int 0x13
jmp 0x50:0x0

hlt

times 510-($-$$) db 0
dw 0xAA55

```

Figure-10: Example Usage of Interrupt 13H

The code in Figure-10 is also an example of an MBR and can be booted by the computer.

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, on x86 IA-16 and IA-32 architectures, BIOS serves as a critical bridge between hardware and the operating system during the system startup process, which begins with the processor executing its first instruction from the reset vector, and ensures the stable booting of the system. Throughout this process, BIOS runs the processor in real mode, performs the initial configuration of memory controllers, interrupt controllers, and basic input/output units, and verifies hardware integrity through POST routines. Architectural features examined within the scope of this study, such as the 1 MB memory limit, A20 line control, and

the Interrupt Vector Table, are evaluated as reflections of the backward compatibility principle in the historical development of x86 platforms. The low-level service routines and interrupt mechanisms provided by BIOS offer a standard abstraction layer for hardware access until the operating system takes control. Ultimately, this technical framework offered by the BIOS architecture forms the foundation of modern firmware structures and is vital for understanding the architectural legacy in the initial system startup processes.

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